

New information on the barkflies (Psocodea) fauna of selected nature reserves in Poland

Nowe dane do fauny gryzków (Psocodea) wybranych rezerwatów Polski

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ABSTRACT: Faunistic data concerning the occurrence of barkflies (Psocodea) in the area of six nature reserves in the Masovian Lowland (11 species) and the Pomeranian Lake District (1 species) were presented. The specimens were collected by sieving the detritus or crushed tree bark particles or by beating the vegetation.

KEY WORDS: barkflies, Psocodea, fauna, distribution, nature reserves, Poland.

Introduction

So far, about 5500 species of barkflies (Psocodea) have been described in the world, and their greatest differentiation occurs in tropical and subtropical zones (LIENHARD 2016). The insects of the order Psocodea are poorly known in Poland. To date, 75 species have been recorded (LIENHARD & SMITHERS 2002). In this short note new distributional data are reported for 13 Psocoptera species. There are a lot of Psocodea specimens in forest and bog biocenoses, they are easily collected by simple standard methods (WŁODARCZYK 1968). However, difficulties in species identification restrain of use of Psocodea for bioindication purposes (OSTROVSKY 2016).

Material and methods

The study was carried out in June 2019 in six nature reserves. Five of them locate in Masovian Lowland (Bukowiec Jabłonowski, Mosty Kalińskie, Łosiowe Błota, Okólny Ług, Horowe Bagno). Natural reserve Żurawie Chrusty locates in Pomeranian Lake District.

The barkflies were collected by sieving the detritus or crushed tree bark particles or by beating the vegetation. They were preserved in 96% ethanol. After identification they were deposited in the collections Artsiom OSTROVSKY (Belarus), and some specimens in the collections dr Dilian GEORGIEV (University of Plovdiv, Bulgaria). Species identifications are based

on key of LIENHARD (1998). As a supporting source, SAVILLE (2008) was also used.

Results

Order Psocodea NOVAK, 1890

Suborder Troctomorpha Roesler, 1940

Infraorder Nanopsocetae BROADHEAD, 1950

Family Liposcelididae BROADHEAD, 1950

Liposcelis sp.

- EC09 Horowe Bagno nature reserve (52.3339°N, 21.1486°E): 9 VI 2019, 1 nymph, pine forest in a borders of bog, collected by sieving; leg. et det. A. OSTROVSKY.

Suborder Psocomorpha Weber, 1936

Infraorder Caeciliusetae Pearman, 1936

Family Caeciliusidae MOCKFORD, 2000

Valenzuela flavidus (STEPHENS, 1836)

- XA92 Żurawie Chrusty nature reserve (54.3361°N, 17.9583°E): 22 VI 2019, 2♀, 1♂, old pine forest, collected by beating the vegetation; leg. et det. A. OSTROVSKY.

Valenzuela piceus (KOLBE, 1882)

- EC19 Mosty Kalińskie nature reserve (52.2958°N, 21.2664°E): 25 VI 2019, 1♀ (brachypterous), mixed forest, collected by beating the vegetation; leg. A. OSTROVSKY, det. D. GEORGIEV.

Infraorder Homilopsocidea PEARMAN, 1936

Family Elipsocidae PEARMAN, 1936

Elipsocus moebiusi TETENS, 1891

- Mosty Kalińskie nature reserve (52.2958°N, 21.2664°E): 25 VI 2019, 1♀, fragment of hornbeam forest, collected by beating the vegetation; leg. A. OSTROVSKY, det. D. GEORGIEV.

Reuterella helvimacula (ENDERLEIN, 1901)

- DD90 Bukowiec Jabłonowski nature reserve (52.3850°N, 20.9389°E): 8 VI 2019, 2♀, hornbeam forest, collected by beating the vegetation; leg. A. OSTROVSKY, det. D. GEORGIEV.
- EC09 Horowe Bagno nature reserve (52.3339°N, 21.1486°E): 9 VI 2019, pine forest in a borders of bog, 10♀, collected by beating the vegetation; leg. A. OSTROVSKY, det. D. GEORGIEV.

Family Mesopsocidae PEARMAN, 1936

Mesopsocus laticeps (KOLBE, 1880)

- EC19 Mosty Kalińskie nature reserve (52.2958°N, 21.2664°E): 25 VI 2019, 1♂, hornbeam forest, collected by beating the vegetation; leg. et det. A. OSTROVSKY.

Family Peripsocidae ROESLER, 1944

Peripsocus alboguttatus (DALMAN, 1823)

- EB39 Okólny Ług nature reserve (51.4300°N, 21.5683°E): 24 VI 2019, 1♀, 1♂, 1 nymph, on willows in the border of bog, collected by beating the vegetation; leg. et det. A. OSTROVSKY.

Peripsocus didymus ROESLER, 1939

- XA92 Żurawie Chrusty nature reserve (54.3361°N, 17.9583°E): 22 VI 2019, 1♀, 1♂, pine forest in a borders of bog, collected by beating the vegetation; leg. et det. A. OSTROVSKY.

Peripsocus subfasciatus (RAMBUR, 1842)

- EC19 Mosty Kalińskie nature reserve (52.2958°N, 21.2664°E): 25 VI 2019, 2♀, pine forest, collected by beating the vegetation; leg. et det. A. OSTROVSKY.

Infraorder Philotarsetae Yoshizawa & Johnson, 2014

Family Philotarsidae PEARMAN, 1936

Philotarsus parviceps ROESLER, 1954

- EC19 Mosty Kalińskie nature reserve (52.2958°N, 21.2664°E): 25 VI 2019, 5♀, 1♂, fragment of hornbeam forest, collected by beating the vegetation; leg. et det. A. OSTROVSKY.

Infraorder Psocetae PEARMAN, 1936

Family Psocidae HAGEN, 1865

Amphigerontia contaminata (STEPHENS, 1836)

- EB39 Okólny Ług nature reserve (51.4300°N, 21.5683°E): 24 VI 2019, 3♀, 13♂, 27 nymph, on old willows, collected by beating the vegetation; leg. et det. A. OSTROVSKY.

Loensia fasciata (FABRICIUS, 1787)

- XA92 Żurawie Chrusty nature reserve (54.3361°N, 17.9583°E): 22 VI 2019, 1♀, pine forest in a borders of bog, collected by beating the vegetation; leg. et det. A. OSTROVSKY.

Metylophorus nebulosus (STEPHENS, 1836)

- DC98 Łosiowe Błota nature reserve (52.2569°N, 20.8611°E): 23 VI 2019, 1♀, pine forest, collected by beating the vegetation; leg. et det. A. OSTROVSKY.
- EB39 Okólny Ług nature reserve (51.4300°N, 21.5683°E): 24 VI 2019, 1♀, on willows in the border of bog, collected by beating the vegetation; leg. et det. A. OSTROVSKY.

Conclusion

According WŁODARCZYK (1968) no barkflies species has been found from the Masovian Lowland, so the provision of faunistic data for at least 11 common species seems justified for comparison: in the neighboring Podlasie presence known only 5 species (SZAWARYN & al. 2020). One species: *Peripsocus didymus* is the first reported for the Pomeranian Lake District.

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SUMMARY

The barkflies (Psocodea) occurring on the territory of Poland are rarely reported in faunistic publications. The distribution data from nature reserve are very fragmentary. To fill this gap we present here new distribution data on the occurrence of 11 species in six nature reserves in Mazowian Lowland (11 species) and Pomeranian Lake District (1 species).

STRESZCZENIE

Przedstawiono dane faunistyczne dotyczące występowania gryzków (Psocodea) na terenie sześciu rezerwatów przyrody na Nizinie Mazowieckiej (11 gatunków) i Pojezierzu Pomorskim (1 gatunek). Materiał zbierano przez przesiewanie detrytusu lub zmiądzzonych części kory drzew, oraz przez otrząsanie się gałęzi roślin.

REFERENCES

- LIENHARD C. 1998. Psocoptères Euro-Méditerranéens. Faune de France, **83**. Paris: Fédération Française des Sociétés de Sciences Naturelles.
- LIENHARD C. 2016. Country checklists of the Psocoptera species of the World. (pp. 1-123). [In:] C. LIENHARD, C. SMITHERS (ed.): Psocoptera (Insecta) – world catalogue and bibliography. Psocid News. Special Issue I.
- LIENHARD C., SMITHERS C. 2002. Psocoptera (Insecta): world catalogue and bibliography. Instrument Biodiversitatis V. Genève, Muséum d'histoire naturelle.
- OSTROVSKY A.M. 2016. Barkflies (Psocoptera) – bioindicators of the ecological state of natural ecosystems of the south-east of Belarus. [In:] A.B. Polonsky et al. (ed.): Environmental Control Systems – 2016. Abstracts of the International research-to-practice conference (Sevastopol, 24 – 27 October 2016)]. Sevastopol: Institute of Natural and Technical Systems. [In Russian]
- SAVILLE B. 2008. (dostęp 16.12.2021)
<https://www.brc.ac.uk/schemes/barkfly/key/key.htm>
- SZAWARYN K., KWIATKOWSKI A., MARCZAK D. 2020. Nowe dane o występowaniu psotników (Psocoptera) na terenie Puszczy Knyszyńskiej. Wiadomości Entomologiczne, **39** (2): 6-7
- WŁODARCZYK J. 1968. Gryzki Psocoptera. Katalog Fauny Polski, XVIII, **11**: 1-41.

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